

occurs annually. Yields of the better lines, including RD17 and RD19, averaged 3 to 4 t/ha; Pin Gaew 56 generally yielded 1 to 2 t/ha less. The yields varied depending on maximum water depth and amount of fertilizer applied. RD17 often averaged 4 t/ha when water depths did not exceed 1 m. Neither variety is recommended for areas where water depths are expected to exceed 1 m.

Both RD17 and RD19 are intended for the monsoon season because they mature too late for the dry-season crop. Also water depth is usually not a problem in the dry season and the present improved varieties such as RD7 perform satisfactorily there.

RD17 is insensitive to photoperiod, has a stiff straw, matures in about

140 days, can elongate its stem at 5 cm/day, and has withstood submergence for 7 days without serious injury. Its drought tolerance at early growth stages is an additional advantage. When grown in 80 cm of water RD17 has an average height of 160 cm (range, 150–170 cm). It is moderately resistant to bacterial blight but susceptible to the brown planthopper, stem borer, and gall midge. RD17 has brown rice kernels more than 7 mm long, with relatively low chalkiness and high amylose content. Its cooking and milling characteristics, however, are acceptable.

We believe that RD17 will become popular in occasionally flooded areas where farmers grow ordinary improved varieties. RD17's elongation ability would be flood insurance in such

high-risk areas. Furthermore, its photoperiod insensitivity will permit many farmers in flood-prone areas to harvest a crop in about 140 days. RD19 is sensitive to photoperiod, and has slightly higher grain chalkiness and better drought tolerance in the vegetative stage than RD17. RD19 usually ripens around mid-December, if planted in July or August. RD19 has acceptable milling and cooking qualities. Its greatest potential is anticipated in areas where farmers now plant only tall, traditional, photoperiod-sensitive types because monsoon floods might destroy ordinary improved varieties. Furthermore, because of its better plant type, RD19 is expected to be more fertilizer responsive than traditional varieties. ■

Structural analysis of the nematode population and the source of ufra

P. G. Cox, L. Rahman, and M. A. Hannan, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI)-Overseas Development Agency (ODA) Deepwater Rice Pest Management Project, BRRI, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Ufra caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev is a serious disease of deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4:3 [June 1979], 10–11) have suggested how structural analysis of the nematode population (i.e. determination of the relative frequency with which different population sizes occur in individual tillers) might be used to identify the source of inoculum according to the presence of a distinct mode at high populations. The presence early in the season of heavily infested tillers might be evidence of primary infestation from diseased residues in the field at sowing, well before flooding.

At BRRI two blocks of deepwater rice (variety Gorcha) were broadcast on 10 April 1979 in a deepwater tank especially constructed for ufra research. At the time of broadcast the larger block (8 × 8 m) was inoculated with 100 infested panicles retained from the previous season; the smaller block

Structure of the ufra nematode population with and without basal inoculation. BRRI, 1979.

(8 × 4 m) was not inoculated. The tank was flooded from early June onward. Active *D. angustus* were collected from a farmer's field and dispersed in the tank on 16 June to simulate secondary infestation by water-borne inoculum. The structure of the nematode populations in the two blocks was analyzed at the end of August through the procedure described by Cox and Rahman.

The two population structures differed greatly (see figure). The plot with basal inoculation had a much greater percentage of infested tillers and average number of nematodes per tiller. The population structure in the inoculated plot also had a distinct right-hand mode representing about 2.5% of all tillers (av no. of nematodes/infested tiller in the RH mode, 5500; s.d. 3700). This mode did not occur in the

uninoculated plot. The results support the idea of equating the presence of a distinct structural mode at high nematode populations with the outcome

of primary crop infestation at about the time of sowing. They also demonstrate the possibility of maintaining different levels of infestation in a single infested

tank despite biological continuity between the plots after the tank is flooded. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Effect of age of tungro-diseased plants on GLH infectivity

A. Hasanuddin and K. C. Ling, *Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute*

The infectivity of the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* was determined by the test-tube inoculation method after feeding the insects on tungro-diseased TN1 plants of different ages. Diseased plants were inoculated 7 days after soaking, kept in the greenhouse for 15, 30, 60, and 90 days, and then used as virus sources for 1,920 adult GLH.

The percentages of infective insects varied among those fed on diseased plants

Infectivity of *Nephotettix virescens* fed on tungro-diseased TN1 plants of different ages, at various acquisition access times.^a

Diseased plant age (days)	Total (no.)	2h	24 h	96 h
Infective insects (%)				
15	480 insects	25 a	48 a	81 b
30	480 insects	55 b	82 b	90 c
60	480 insects	46 b	74 b	85 c
90	480 insects	20 a	29 a	62 a
Retention period (days)				
15	321 insects	1.2 a	1.4 a	1.8 b
30	345 insects	1.7 a	1.9 a	2.1 b
60	337 insects	1.7 a	1.9 a	1.8 b
90	363 insects	1.6 a	1.6 a	1.3 a
Infected seedlings (%)				
15	3,302 seedlings	5 a	9a	21 b
30	3,320 seedlings	13 a	20 a	28 c
60	3,304 seedlings	10 a	19 a	21 b
90	3,304 seedlings	5 a	6a	10 a

^aMeans followed by a common letter in each column are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Effect of tungro-infected source plants of different ages on percentage of rice green leafhoppers infective at acquisition access periods of 2,24, and 96 hours.

of different ages, regardless of acquisition access time (2, 24, or 96 hours) (see figure). At 96 hours access time, a higher percentage of the insects that fed on 30- and 60-day diseased plants became infective, had a longer infectivity retention period, and infected a greater

percentage of seedlings than the insects that fed on 15- or 90-day diseased plants (see table).

The variation in the insects' infectivity indicated that diseased plants of different ages were not identical in quality as virus sources. ■

Checking infection of rice root nematode by nursery treatment and bare root dips to increase yield

T. Venkitesan, *nematologist, and Job Satyakumar Charles, research assistant, All India Coordinated Research Project on Nematode Pests or Crops and their Control, College of Agriculture, Vellayani 695522; and V. Ramachandran Nair, agronomist, Agronomic Research Station, Karamana 695002, Kerala, India*

Six pesticides — aldicarbsulfone, carbofuran, dimethoate, monocrotophos, phosphamidon, and quinalphos — were tested as bare root dip treatment for control of the rice root nematode

Hirschmanniella oryzae. Seedlings of the rice cultivar Triveni were raised in nursery beds treated with and without 30 liters DBCP/ha. They were transplanted in 4-m² microplots in the field after a 12-hour bare root dip in 0.02% pesticide solution. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Differences in nematode population between the check plots and the plots planted to seedlings that received both the DBCP treatment and the bare root dip with phosphamidon were significant. At planting, soil from plots with the treated seedlings had 202 nematodes, and soil from the check plots had 185. At harvest the former had 79 nematodes